

Information, Special Relativity and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

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In previous notes, we have argued that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the special relativistic Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$, which is degenerate for $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$, where n is an integer. From this, one may obtain $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$.

Here, we wish to consider the emergence of the resolutions \hbar/p and \hbar/E from information considerations. In particular, we start with a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest. This means that velocity=0 and the particle in principle can be at any x point. In other words, there is no x information. If the particle were moving there would be x information linked with a unit time interval because the particle has to move a certain dx in this time unit. As a result, v and x are connected. We suggest, however, that it is really p that one should consider because special relativity deals with frames moving at constant $-v$ (as an example). A particle at rest is seen as moving from a moving frame. This, however, is equivalent to applying a force to the particle and so p , which is proportional to impulse, is more appropriate than v . It is also p and E which emerge from transforming $(0, m_0cc)$ using a Lorentz transformation.

Thus, $p=0$ and x having an infinite range are linked in the rest frame only. We note that stating that x has infinite range and hence a uniform probability over this range if $p=0$ is a strong statement. One might try to counter by arguing that a particle moving with constant v not equal to 0 may also be at any x point, hence the infinite range (zero resolution) has nothing to do with $p=0$. We show, however, that the Lorentz transformation maps $x=0, t_1$ and $x=0, t_2$ to two different x' points, hence two different positions of a moving particle may be linked to the same x point in the rest frame at different times. Thus, it is the decoupled $x-t$ rest frame picture which really represents a particle which may be at any x point with equal probability and this uniform probability range decreases when p not equal to 0. If $pdx=1$, we suggest that $Edt=1$ as well. In the rest frame, this means that $m_0cc dt=1$. We have already argued in a previous note that m_0 is proportional to the probability for an internal decay and that on average this occurs with a frequency proportional to m_0 . Thus, the time period is proportional to $1/m_0cc$.

Thus, in principle, we argue one may obtain the resolutions \hbar/p and \hbar/E without using $A = -Et + px$. We further argue that the infinite range of x only holds in the rest frame and so is linked to $p=0$. In other words, a probabilistic viewpoint exists in the rest frame and carries over into other frames so that the $-Edt + pdx=0$ in all frames. Free particle quantum mechanics seems to be linked to this view and so quantum mechanics is a theory which links spatial probability regions (wavelengths) to momentum, we argue.

Special Relativity

A key feature of special relativity is that one may take a rest mass, m_0 , at rest, at $x=0$ and t and view it from different frames moving at various constant velocity, v , values. This gives rise to new concepts of p (momentum= $m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$) and energy ($E=m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$). In principle, in the rest frame $E=m_0cc$ and $p=0$. Momentum only exists (is nonzero) if there is a velocity and this in turn requires information about a dx in a unit of time.

In the rest frame, $p=0$, $v=0$ and the particle may be anywhere in space, i.e. have any x . Thus, there is no information about x present. The momentum $=0$ and so there is information about this value. In the Lorentz transformed frame, there is a new p value, but this represents only one piece of information and there is a corresponding one piece of momentum information in the rest frame. The problem is that there is no x information in the rest frame (any x is as good as the other), but now there is a specific dx' value, i.e. $x'/t' = v$. Another way to view this is to note that x and t are decoupled in the rest frame, but not in the moving frame, so there is something special about the rest frame in terms of the probability distribution of x .

The new spatial information has arisen for the same physical state. Viewing a state at rest from a moving frame does not change the physical nature of the state. In other words, we suggest that one is still dealing with the same physical state even if viewed from a moving frame and that one description (rest frame) cannot contain more information than the other. We thus suggest that the extra dx' information required in the moving frame must somehow be linked to p' . In fact, x' and p' transform in the same manner via the Lorentz transformation. We suggest, however, that one introduce the idea of a dx' gradation in the moving frame such that:

$$P' dx' = \text{constant} \quad \text{or} \quad dx' = \text{constant}/p' = \hbar/p' \quad ((1))$$

In the rest frame, the ruler gradation is infinite because for $v=0$, $p=0$, the particle can be anywhere in x , i.e. an infinite ruler gradation. These are not independent notions (i.e. $p=0$ and $= \text{infinite}$) so we suggest that:

$$Dx p = \text{constant} = \hbar \quad ((2))$$

As a result, ((1)) and ((2)) ensure the same amount of p and dx information in both the rest and moving frames.

The statement ((1)) arguing that a particle can be at any x point because it has $p=0$ is quite strong. We suggest that the uniform probability distribution only applies to an object at rest. Thus, it is only the $p=0$ case which really allows for an infinite range in x or 0 x resolution. One might try to counter and argue that if a particle moves with a nonzero constant v , it may be at any x point and hence this is also an infinite range which has nothing to do with $p=0$. Using the Lorentz transformation, however,

$$\begin{aligned} |g(v) \quad vg(v)| \quad ((2b)) \quad g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \\ |vg(v) \quad g(v)| \end{aligned}$$

one may see that $x=0$, t_1 and $x=0$, t_2 in the rest frame map to the two x' points:

$$X' 1 = vg(v) t_1 \quad \text{and} \quad x' 2 = vg(v) t_2 \quad ((2c))$$

Thus, a single x point in the rest frame may map to different x' points in the moving frame depending on the time t_1 . We argue that in the moving frame, one cannot really consider that all x' points have the same probability weight as a result. We also note that in the moving frame, x'

and t' are not decoupled as in the rest frame because $x'/t'=v$ (if one has $x=0, t=0$ and $x'=0, t'=0$). The rest frame is special because the probability or resolution of x in this frame is unique. X can take on any value in a probabilistic manner because $p=0$. This changes when one is in a moving frame, but to ensure that the physical state is the same, pdx does not change. This is the main point of this note.

An independent argument using m_0 as being proportional to an internal frequency is given later.

The Situation with dt and Rest Mass

In the rest frame, one has rest mass, m_0 , and any time one wishes. If one treats x and ct on the same footing, then the relation ((2)) in the rest frame suggests that one consider:

$$m_0 c dt = \text{constant} = \hbar \quad ((3))$$

In the moving frame, one has t' and E and so one should have:

$$E dt' = \hbar \quad ((4))$$

In this manner, one seems to consider m_0 as a scaled value which acts with an inverse dt to remove all information of m_0 in the product $m_0 dt$. In other words, this is an invariant which goes beyond the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, and actually removes energy and momentum information so as to describe all free particle energies and momenta with dt and dx 's on the same footing.

The Notion of Scaling

We have already discussed in a previous note that the inverse relation between m_0 and dt may be linked to m_0 being considered proportional to an internal probability to decay. On average this probability defines dt units through $1/m_0$ because if one doubles the mass, one doubles the probability which doubles the frequency of decays or halves the period. This argument, linked to internal decay, basically suggests the notion of scaling for m_0 and period because all m_0 are really made of the same material. This scaling argument, however, seems to only go down to the length scale at which a decay occurs. It is, however, a probabilistic argument as is the notion that $p=0$ means that x can be at any x point. This idea of probability in the rest frame differs from the deterministic Lorentz transformation and also classical mechanics.

Link with a Lorentz Invariant

We have argued that $pdx = \text{constant}$ and $E dt = \text{constant}$. This implies that:

$$-E dt + p dx = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad d(A = \text{constant}) = -E dt + p dx \quad ((4b))$$

Here E and p are constant because m_0 and v are not changing. Thus, one should have the invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad (4c)$$

which indeed exists in special relativity.

The Role of $\exp(ipx)$

We have argued that the $p \, dx = E \, dt = \hbar$. This suggests a uniform probability distribution in t and x in specific \hbar/E and \hbar/p regions, but space consists of all x , t values. Thus, these resolution units must be enforced somehow, by having the uniform probability combined with a shell probability which is linked with 0 probability at the endpoints of the intervals \hbar/p , \hbar/E . Space and time, however, are uniform. They are not broken into discrete time and x units overtly for a free particle, so one has to introduce a complex function $\exp(ipx)$ such that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ respects this overall uniformity of space, while px and Et ($\exp(-iEt)\exp(iEt) = 1$) shows uniform probability within \hbar/p and \hbar/E units. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ as well as $\cos(Et)$, $\sin(Et)$ enforce the 0 values at the endpoints so that there is actually a way to see the intervals as shown in a 2-slit experiment. On average, however, $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ washes out these intervals. Thus, probability is involved and a two dimensional function $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in numerous previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the degeneracy in the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$, i.e. $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$, where n is an integer. Here we do not use this invariant, but rather rely on the idea of the amount of information. In a rest frame, a rest mass m_0 sits at $x=0$ with $p=v=0$. $x=0$ is not really spatial information, because x can really take on any value. In other words, one has a probabilistic viewpoint for x with a uniform probability over all x and 0 x resolution. Our main point is that this situation only holds in the rest frame in which x and t are decoupled. One might try to argue that a particle moving with constant v also can be at any x point, hence the 0 x resolution has nothing to do with $p=0$. We argue, however, that $x=0, t_1$ and $x=0, t_2$ map into different x' points under a Lorentz transformation. Thus, we do not consider all x points having equal weight for a constantly moving particle, only one at rest.

We use the idea that the particle at rest is linked to the moving particle and so there should be some probabilistic link as well. If one uses $p \, dx = \hbar$ in the rest frame and also applies this to $m \, dc = \hbar \, dt$, then $-E \, dt + p \, dx = 0$ or $d(A = \text{constant}) = 0$ so $A = -Et + px$ which is a Lorentz invariant. The relation $m \, dc = \hbar \, dt$ may be obtained by considering rest mass proportional to the probability of an internal decay which on average defines a frequency $= 1/T$ period. Hence, $T = \hbar/E$ (using \hbar as a constant).